

IPERION HS

CALL: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1

GA n. 871034

D6.4 Implementation strategy for IPR management

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Document information

Project number	871034	Acronym	IPERION HS
Full title	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science		
Project url	www.iperionhs.eu		
EU Project Officer	António Ventura		

Deliverable	Number	D6.4	Title	Implementation strategy for IPR management
Work Package	Number	6	Title	Innovation and exploitation

Deliverable nature	<input type="checkbox"/> prototype <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> report <input type="checkbox"/> demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> other		
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted		
Contractual delivery date	31/10/2023		
Actual delivery date	31/07/2023		
Status	Version 0.5	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final	

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Total number of pages	20
Keywords	IPR, IR, E-RIHS, ERIC

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. no.	Author	Change
17/01/2022	0.1	Ohad Graber-Soudry	1 st draft shared
28/01/2022	0.2	Ohad Graber-Soudry	Integrating comments from stakeholders and interim version
26/01/2023	0.3	Ohad Graber-Soudry	Work on 2 nd draft
21/03/2023	0.4	Ohad Graber-Soudry	Review of close-to-final version
20/07/2023	0.5	Ohad Graber-Soudry	Final version

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1. Abstract

E-RIHS is a distributed research infrastructure in the field of heritage science - an interdisciplinary research domain spanning the humanities, arts, environment, engineering and sciences. Heritage science encompasses all forms of scientific enquiry into objects, buildings and landscape sites that are endowed with cultural or historical value.

One of the main objectives of E-RIHS is to provide its user community with common access to instruments and scientific data through unified entry points and harmonised procedures. E-RIHS will not own the heritage research objects or data produced or held by its Partners, but will facilitate the sharing and reuse of research data produced and exchange of knowledge in general.

It is important to prevent situations where the sharing and re-use of research data by the E-RIHS Partners or other researchers made available through E-RIHS research infrastructure inadvertently breach the rights of data owners or third parties' IPR (mainly copyright). This is because the way in which research data is produced and described may automatically create copyrights if the description contains a creative element (hence rendering the data "copyrightable").

This report provides a plan and strategy for IPR management so as to ensure that copyright or other related rights shall not become an obstacle to the use, reuse and sharing of data by Users of E-RIHS, unless legal restrictions, legitimate reasons or other justified considerations apply. This can be achieved, among others, through a system of open licensing for use by E-RIHS Partners and Data Owners. In some cases, there may be legal or legitimate reasons to retain access and re-use of data or parts of it restricted. Equally, embargo periods may need to be applied in order to allow researchers to work-up their data sets and publish their findings. The FAIR principles do not prevent from recognising such legal and legitimate reasons for shielding data and restricting disclosure of the data but require that data should be findable and the conditions of access and reuse are clearly set out in the metadata.

Finally, this report also acknowledges that in specific cases, activities services or knowledge produced by E-RIHS or its Partners may have a potential for commercial exploitation or for other justified purposes. In such cases, there may be a need to consider IPR protection to allow for technology transfer and commercialisation and to be clear on the allocation of such IPR.

2. Outline

The report is organised as follows:

Section 1 provides a short abstract.

Section 2 provides an outline of the report.

Section 3 “Abbreviations” provides a short explanation of the key terms that are used throughout this report in order to provide clarity and precision for the reader.

Section 4 “Introduction” provides relevant background to E-RIHS, setting the context and outline the rationale for the creation of this report.

Section 5 “Basic concepts” explains important concepts used in the report and sets the scene for the next section on the principles for IPR management.

Section 6 “Principles for IPR management” presents a holistic view for E-RIHS IPR management plan and provides for a strategy to be applied in connection with the goal of facilitating the sharing of the scientific benefit and work done within the E-RIHS research infrastructure with Users, without breaching copyright and by using a system that includes open licensing.

Section 7 “Implementation” provides a list of specific licenses recommended for use by E-RIHS Partners, Data Owners and Data Providers when making their research data available through the E-RIHS ERIC.

Section 8 “Conclusions” closes this report with a summary of the guidance provided in this report.

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3. Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
Background	Refers to IP owned by a E-RIHS Partner that is related to the Partner's contribution or participation in the E-RIHS, but has not been created as a result of work carried out in connection with E-RIHS. It is IP which is already in existence and held by a Partner prior to its involvement in E-RIHS. Background IP can represent an important component of a Partner's contribution (including in-kind) to E-RIHS.
CC BY license	The CC BY open licence which allows everyone to re-use, distribute and modify the licensed materials. The licence requires users to give credit (attribution) to the creator.
CC BY-NC license	The CC BY-NC licence is the same as the CC BY with the added restriction that any derivative work must be for non-commercial use only.
CC 0 license	The Creative Commons No Rights Reserved license, which means that the rightsholder(s) waives its copyrights in the work so it is left in the public domain.
Copyright	One of the intellectual property rights, which is characterized by the fact that it confers on its holder rights upon a literary and artistic work.
Creative Commons (CC)	A not-for-profit organisation which makes a number of open licences available for copyright (or database rights) protected works. The structure of the CC licences is based on a number of building blocks, which may be combined in a number of different ways.
Data Owner	The person or legal entity possessing the Copyright or any other relevant intellectual property rights of the data (e.g., the one creating the data). The Data Owner may or may not be identical to the Data Provider.
Database	A collection of independent works, data or other materials arranged in a systematic or methodical way and individually accessible by electronic or other means. ¹
Data Provider	The person or legal entity making the data available through E-RIHS ERIC (e.g. the Principal Investigator, or the Partner, etc.).
Embargo Period	Is a period of time where an access restriction is applied to a piece of data and/or other research output, whereby the item will not be made available as Open Access until a predetermined time.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud, a European Commission initiative that is being developed as a globally accessible, multidisciplinary data infrastructure. The EOSC will federate the existing scientific data and digital infrastructures for data exploitation that are now spread across disciplines and EU Member States.
FAIR Principles	A set of guiding principles that seek to increase the reusability of data and digital objects (including data-related algorithms, tools, workflows, protocols, services and other kinds of digital and research objects). FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

¹ Directive 96/9/EC (the "Database Directive").

Foreground	Refers to IP generated in the course of an E-RIHS project by E-RIHS itself, or by a Partners alone or together with E-RIHS, arising out of an E-RIHS project.
GDPR	The General Data Protection Regulation European Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on data protection and privacy.
Intellectual Policy Rights (IPR)	Rights given to persons over the creations of their minds. They usually give the creator an exclusive right over the use of his/her creation for a certain period of time. It is further defined in Article 2 of the Convention Establishing the World Intellectual Property Organisation of 14 July 1967.
Interoperability	The ability of two or more systems or components to exchange information and to use the information that has been exchanged.
Metadata	Data that contains descriptive, contextual and provenance assertions about the properties of research data or a digital object. It provides systematic descriptions and attributes of data relevant to interpret what the data concerns.
Open Access	A set of principles and practices through which research outputs are distributed online, free of cost or other access barriers. Copying or reuse are also reduced or removed by applying an open license for copyright.
Open License	A license which allows others to reuse another creator's work as they wish.
Open Science	A movement that encourages the research community to be open, not only with their results, but also as they conduct their research, i.e., extending the principles of openness to the whole research cycle.
Partner or E-RIHS Partner	Partner institutions connected to the E-RIHS research infrastructure, representing relevant scientific communities.
Users or E-RIHS Users	Individuals and institutions from academia, business, industry and public services that are granted access to E-RIHS resources and services.
Waiver	The owner of the copyright waives their rights to be identified as the author or owner of the work in question and/or their right to object to derogatory treatment of the work. The work is then released to the public domain without copyrights.

4. Introduction

E-RIHS is a distributed research infrastructure in the field of heritage science - an interdisciplinary research domain spanning the humanities, arts, environment, engineering and sciences. Heritage science encompasses all forms of scientific enquiry into objects, buildings, landscape sites, cultural and natural history collections, architectural heritage and monuments as well as archaeological and geological sites, that are endowed with cultural or historical value. It seeks to enhance the understanding, preservation, care and sustainable use of heritage and thereby contributes to social cohesion and well-being of our current and future society, through the studies of our past. The practice of heritage science may also lead to innovation, particularly when used in combination with digital technologies that facilitate research and ease of collaboration and may enrich other scientific fields and industries.

E-RIHS' mission is to promote cutting edge interdisciplinary research by, among others, providing a central access point to partners' resources, including digital data, reference collections, laboratory and mobile infrastructures, various services and facilities including the continuous development of open access to material and digital scientific resources.

Intellectual Property may be produced as a consequence of E-RIHS activities, or when E-RIHS will need to use the IPRs of its Partners, in-kind providers, and of other third parties. In this report the term Intellectual Property includes, but is not limited to, patents, copyright, trademarks, trade secrets, database rights, know-how and confidentiality obligations. It is used to describe a bundle of intangible assets associated with heritage science such as data, databases, know-how and practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills, instruments, objects, artefacts and cultural spaces associated with communities, which are recognized as part of their cultural heritage.² However it is assumed that most of the IPR associated with E-RIHS activities will concern copyright.

Although the E-RIHS ERIC will not own the heritage research objects themselves, it is envisaged that E-RIHS ERIC will facilitate the sharing of the scientific benefit of Partners' work with the user community. Similarly, E-RIHS ERIC will not own the data produced by its Partners, but it should facilitate the reuse of such data, through a system that may involve open licensing.

While factual data, artefacts or datasets that contain merely facts are not eligible for IP (copyright) protection, the way in which artefacts or data are described may be copyrightable if the description contains a creative element and if there is more than a limited number of ways to describe the artefacts or the data. Even metadata may contain creative elements, for example, if the metadata contains a short summary or a creative description of the artefact or the data, that part of the metadata may be automatically protected by copyright. A 'creative element' refers to an original and creative expression that an author or creator adds to a work. The creative element is what makes a work protectable under copyright law. In other words, copyright protection applies only to original works that contain creative expressions.

The use and re-use of such data by E-RIHS Users and researchers may inadvertently breach copyright. For example, if a photo is embedded in a dataset, the photo may be subject to a

² UNESCO, Convention for Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage, Art. 2(1). See <https://ich.unesco.org/en/convention>.

separate licence, and it may not always be easy to identify the correct copyright holder and/or applicable licence. A researcher using the photo may also not be aware of the scope of copyright related to this component and could therefore inadvertently infringe a third party's copyright when presenting the photo or publishing the photo as part of its work. If the copyright to the photo is owned by an E-RIHS Partner or a Data Owner, then it should be clear how that E-RIHS Partner or the Data Owner intend to license the photo so that Users who are granted access to the photo could make use of it without breaching any copyright associated with the photo. If the copyright to the photo is owned by a third party, then guidance should be available to researchers on which terms they may use or re-publish the photo.

One of the main objectives of E-RIHS is to provide its Users with common access to instruments and scientific data through unified entry points and harmonised procedures. Recent data policies recommended by funding bodies require scientists to make available the data which underpin their research results.³ Collaboration is essential to avoid duplication of investments and fragmentation of research efforts and for this purpose E-RIHS should aim at fostering a culture of interdisciplinarity, exchange and cooperation associating researchers from the required disciplines on equal level.

At the same time, in specific cases E-RIHS and/or its Partners may explore the possibility whether the activities they carry out under their work programmes or otherwise may generate Foreground (i.e., intellectual property rights) with a potential for commercial exploitation. For example, art characterisation such as technical and physical analysis, composition, structure of the artwork, etc. carried out by E-RIHS or by a Partner may be transformed to a service offered to the market, supporting authentication procedures, i.e., using cultural heritage science to derive the state of conservation of an artwork. The service offered could take the form of issuing a scientific certificate that could be used for evaluation or other market-related purposes by the insurance market or by auction houses and private collectors that require objective evaluation of the state of conservation of an artwork. In such cases, there may be legitimate reasons to protect IP assets to allow for technology transfer and commercialisation of the service so specific measures should be taken to protect the IP asset (be it a trade secret, know-how, copyright or filing for a patent).

Similarly, embargo periods may be applied in specific cases, for example, when researchers wish to protect their research by applying a reasonable amount of time to work-up their data sets and publish their findings.

This report provides a plan and strategy for IPR management so as make research data available for use and reuse by others through a system involving the use of open access and/or open licensing (unless legal or legitimate reasons apply) but also creating exceptions to support protection of IP in justified cases. A number of sources have been consulted in the preparation of this report, including:

- Desk research and analysis of literature, guidelines and web-based publications concerning IPR principles, copyright policies, open data, FAIR principles and data policies.

³ See for example "Guidelines on Implementation of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in projects supported by the European Research Council under Horizon 2020" available at https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/oa-pilot/h2020-hi-erc-oa-guide_en.pdf. See also section 1.3 on Open Science in the "Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)", version 1.1 – November 2022, available at: <https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/SRIA%201.1%20final.pdf>

- Interviews conducted with experts from the E-RIHS network in order to gain a better understanding of the unique IP and data-related issues that concern Partners and stakeholders in E-RIHS. Interviews were conducted with the following individuals who agreed to share their knowledge and thoughts with us:
 - Fabio Maria Montagnino, Head of Innovation and Entrepreneurship at the Cyprus Institute.
 - Jakub Novotný, Director of CET, Institute of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics CAS.
 - Corina Bors, National Museum of History, Romania.
 - Gideon Avni, Chief Scientist at the Israel Antiquities Authority
 - Catalina Martínez, Scientist at the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)

- The work completed under D.4.4 on 'IPR Management rules' as well as discussions within the members of WP6, particularly with the task leaders.

5. Basic concepts

Copyright

Copyright is an intellectual property right that grants authors or creators of an original work the exclusive right to reproduce or otherwise communicate the work and also to make adaptations and modifications to the work. Copyright protection is obtained automatically: it arises from the moment the work is created, and no registration or other formality is required. This means that if such automatic rights are not waived, or if there is no clarity regarding the legal conditions under which a work may be used (i.e., a license), the ability of researchers to access and reuse the work is restricted.

Observed or measured facts, as such, are considered to be “discovered” rather than “created” and therefore factual data or datasets that contain merely facts are not eligible for copyright protection. However, the way in which facts or data are described may be copyrightable if the description contains a creative element and if there is more than a limited number of ways to describe the facts or the data. Even metadata may contain creative elements, for example, if the metadata contains a short summary or a creative description of the data, that part of the metadata may be automatically protected by copyright. In addition, the compilation or collection of data into a dataset or database may be subject to copyright. In such a case it is the collection itself, not the facts or data in the collection, which is protected under copyright (and potentially *sui generis* rights), provided that the collection is an intellectual creation of an original collection.

Intangible assets connected to heritage science may be copyright-protected assets if they contain a creative element. These may include photographic images of artifacts and artworks, audio recordings, audio-visual works, multimedia productions, publications and educational material, databases of information about collections, etc.

Important to note, as mentioned, that copyright protection is obtained automatically, as it arises from the moment the work is created and no registration or other formality is required. This means that if such automatic rights are not waived, or if there is no clarity regarding the legal conditions under which a work may be shared and re-used, the ability of researchers to access and reuse the data is impaired and so does interoperability and data reusability, because researchers may not be able to combine different datasets from multiple sources in order to create an additional work.

Therefore, before reusing data, it is important that repositories, disseminators and users of data ascertain whether the data, parts of it, or other embedded elements in the data (e.g., pictures or flowcharts) are subject to copyright protection. If the data or parts of it contain an element which falls under copyright protection, then that protected element(s) of the data require a licence or a waiver of rights before the data or dataset may be reused by third parties.

Open Access

The Open Access principle is based on the premise that publicly funded research outputs such as publications, data, software, models, algorithms, workflows, virtual research environments or any other type of research products, should be freely available for use and reuse by others, unless specific restrictions apply (e.g., for protection of personal data, confidentiality, security, applicable law and regulations, secrecy, etc.).⁴ Further, the Open Access principle also covers the use of open research infrastructures for knowledge and data sharing, measures to ensure reproducibility of results and open collaboration within science and with other knowledge actors. Article 24 of the draft E-RIHS ERIC Statutes provides that “E-RIHS ERIC shall promote Open Source, Open Access, and FAIR (findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) principles”.

FAIR Data

The FAIR Data Principles seek to increase the reusability of data and digital objects (including data-related algorithms, tools, workflows, protocols, services and other kinds of digital and research objects). They put specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use data, in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals. FAIR is discussed within the context of Open Science – a movement that encourages researchers and the research community to be open, not only with their results, but also as they conduct their research. The FAIR Principles apply to data regardless of whether access to the data is publicly available, i.e., whether the data is open. FAIR data may or may not be (fully or immediately) open and an access level to data may be set at “FAIR but not open”, so that the FAIR Principles do not restrict the recognition of legitimate and necessary reasons for shielding data and restricting access in justified cases. The FAIR Principles merely require that data should be findable and the conditions of access and reuse are clearly set out, with the availability of contextual and supporting information (metadata), ideally through an automatic authentication and authorisation process.

⁴ See in this regard Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information; Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/499 of 1 March 2023 on a Code of Practice on the management of intellectual assets for knowledge valorisation in the European Research Area.

Metadata

Metadata is data that contains descriptive, contextual and provenance assertions about the properties of the research data. It provides systematic descriptions and attributes of data relevant to interpret what the data concerns. More broadly, it refers to all data about data, such as: structure and internal coherence, source references and licences, time-stamped changes to the data, quality, context, methods and techniques used as well as provenance and context relevant to the proper interpretation and reusability of the data.

Metadata and data are two separate things and should be treated as such. In particular, the FAIR principles requires that metadata standards are articulated, and that metadata is made publicly available to the greatest extent possible, even if the data itself is not fully open or where the data is no longer available or even destroyed.

Finally, for metadata to be useful, it must be standardised and both machine and human readable to enable advanced research techniques. Where access to data is subject to restrictions or certain conditions, this should be stated clearly and consistently in the metadata.

Database

Data as such is not considered to be covered by the term ‘database’, but only the “collections” of such data (or other materials), with the exclusion of independent works such as a recording, audio-visual, cinematographic, literary or musical work.

Databases will be automatically protected by:

- Copyright: if the selection or arrangement of the contents are the author’s own intellectual creation, in which case copyright protection applies to the structure of the database (separately and in addition to any copyrightable content of the database).
- *Sui generis* right:⁵ protecting the “investment” in obtaining, verifying or presenting the contents of a database (as a compilation of data). This database right offers protection in circumstances where copyright protection is not available based on the resources that database makers invest at the moment of creating, updating and presenting the content of database.

Licensing

In order to ensure the use and re-use of research data and heritage science resources by Users, data shared through E-RIHS should carry a license in which the Data Owner and/or Provider (as may be the case) grants Users the right to reuse and modify the research data. The more the license is open and permissive (i.e., the data is open), the less impediments to usage and interoperability will occur. In the case of copyright (or *sui generis* rights), the easiest and most effective way to achieve openness is to waive all rights and make the data part of the public

⁵ A special IP right “sui generis database right (SGDR)”

domain, using the CC 0 license for example (as further discussed below), or alternatively, by using one of the least restrictive licences available. A licence such as the CC BY is a permissive licence that only requires that credit is given to the author of the original work and are preferable over licences that introduce additional conditions or restrictions.

Open access and permissive licensing forms relevant to E-RIHS include, but are not limited to, Creative Commons license (for journal publications, graphics and media as well as *sui generis* database rights) and open source licenses for software⁶, which should facilitate interoperability.

When the intention is to make data (and metadata) available for reuse without restrictions, it is often conducted by way of dedicating the work to the public domain or waiving all rights to the data, to the extent permissible under law. The two most common forms for this purpose are:

- The Creative Commons No Rights Reserved (CC 0), commonly used for both databases and other copyrightable objects, and means that the Data Owner waives its copyrights in the data; or
- The Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and Licence (PDDL), which is primarily used for databases, and places the data in the public domain.

Important to note however that in many jurisdictions the moral right to a copyrightable object cannot be waived.

Traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expression

Traditional Knowledge (TK) is technical know-how, practices, skills, and innovations developed by a traditional, regional, indigenous or local community. As such, it is embedded in the knowledge system of a traditional community and can have a specific meaning in its culture. For instance, some forms of TK can be considered sacred and can be used only by certain members of a traditional community.

Traditional Cultural Expression (TCE) are cultural manifestations such as music, art, designs, symbols and performances. The nature of TCEs primarily subjects them to copyright, trademark, certification of marks, industrial design and appellations of origin.

TK and TCE are not afforded the same level of protection globally and in some jurisdictions, they are not protected at all.⁷ Some resources are protected by communities' customary rules which may not be recognised and enforced by the country in which the community lives or outside of that country and therefore may not be considered as IP or otherwise protected material.

The place of TK and TCE, in particular within conventional intellectual property structures, is therefore uncertain. As mentioned, there is also a great deal of variability between jurisdictions in the way that TK and TCE are being protected, if at all. When protected, it may be by the modern IP model or by a traditional customary model, but the two systems are not necessarily compatible

⁶ <https://opensource.org/licenses/>

⁷ Some countries protect such resources under their IP system either by qualifying them as a special category of protected subject matter of an IP system or without qualifying them as a special category of protected subject matter of IP.

with each other. Some of these problems have been addressed by the development and use of traditional knowledge licences (for example, the No Copyright – Other Known Legal Restrictions rights statement)⁸ to promote legal and respectful use of data.

Access policy

Given the structure and distribution of the E-RIHS, the resources, including data available is diverse, but access to this data is envisaged to be through a central point of access to all resources. The conditions of access by users to E-RIHS ERIC infrastructure facilities and resources, will be governed by a separate E-RIHS ERIC Access Policy.

Embargo period

Embargo period is a period during which access to data is not available on the basis of Open Access unless a specific arrangement is made. What this means in practice is that if a User wishes to access certain datasets during the embargo period, he or she may have to wait until the embargo period has expired before they can access the data or alternatively, try to negotiate an earlier release with the Data Owner on a case-by-case basis.

Other restrictions on access to and use of data

FAIR data is not equivalent to Open Access. The “A” in FAIR stands for “Accessible under well-defined conditions”, implying that there may be legal or other legitimate reasons to retain access and re-use of data or parts of it restricted. In the case of copyright, the easiest and most effective way to maximise sharing of data is to waive all rights and make the data part of the public domain, using the CC 0 license for example. If the data needs to be licensed, it would be best to use one of the least restrictive licences available. Licences such as the CC BY is a permissive licence that only requires that credit (attribution) is given to the author of the original work and are preferable in terms of interoperability over licences that introduce additional conditions or restrictions.

The CC BY-NC license, limiting re-use to non-commercial purposes is sometimes preferred by institutions as a more appropriate alternative to the CC BY. It aims at preventing commercial initiatives that try to monetize Open Access and make economic gain from what could be legitimately considered as work of others. This is something that could be considered by E-RIHS but it also must be measured against the limitations that the CC BY-NC may have. For example, the CC BY-NC could potentially become a barrier to non-commercial reuse due to ambiguities about what constitutes ‘commercial’ and ‘non-commercial’ reuse in research activities. Another problem with the CC BY-NC license is that in certain cases, it may compromise legal interoperability, i.e., the ability to combine datasets from multiple sources without conflicts among the restrictions that each dataset carries. For example, the licenses CC BY-NC and CC BY-SA are not interoperable, that is, they cannot be combined and carried forward to new work (while the CC BY is interoperable with any license, including CC BY-SA).

⁸ <https://rightsstatements.org/en/>

In practice, there will be cases where, for legitimate or regulatory reasons such as privacy, national security, sensitive information, etc., data needs to be shielded or restricted for certain uses. The degree to which any such data is made available is at the discretion of the Data Owner and according to applicable policies. In such cases, different methods may be used, such as generalisation of data, redaction of specific information, anonymisation, embargo periods, etc. However, there will be cases where no such methods would be sufficient and a standard open licence may not be suitable, so the Data Owner will need a customised licence or a specific contract regulating access to the data. This may impair interoperability and ability to share the data but may be necessary. The guiding principle is that data should be kept “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

6. Principles for IPR management

In light of the analysis above, the following principles are recommended in connection with the goal of facilitating the sharing of the scientific benefit and work done within the E-RIHS research infrastructure with Users and removing IP obstacles through a system involving open licensing:

Open Access as a general rule

- As a general rule, the impact of copyrights and other forms of IPR should be minimised to the extent possible, by using appropriate open licenses. Copyright shall not become an obstacle to the use, reuse and sharing of data by Users of E-RIHS, unless legal restrictions, legitimate reasons or other justified considerations apply. For this purpose, intellectual property rights should be clearly defined in order to make the results openly accessible while preventing others from imposing restrictions on them.
- E-RIHS should promote freedom of use by guiding Data Owners and Data Providers to assign open access licenses, such as CC 0 or CC BY whenever possible taking into account third party licences and any pre-existing arrangements. A list of recommended licenses are set out in Section 7 below (“Implementation”).
- In justified cases, Open Access principles should be balanced against legal restrictions, legitimate reasons or where other justified considerations apply. Measures used to restrict access to legally restricted or sensitive data may include embargo periods, authorisation procedures, specific contractual arrangements, etc. In order to remain FAIR, any restrictions or conditions applicable, must be set out clearly in the metadata.
- When the Data Owner is not the Data Provider, then an agreement should be reached between the Data Provider and the Data Owner concerning the use of IP and the associated obligations. Such an agreement could also establish issues related to liabilities for any issue raising from a breach of IP rights by Users.

FAIR Data

- New data made available through E-RIHS shall be FAIR by design and in line with the E-RIHS ERIC Data Policy.

Metadata

- Collection, storage and curation of data should be done with accurate metadata so as to fulfil the FAIR principles and facilitate uninterrupted access to data, to the extent possible and where relevant, subject to additional conditions.
- Metadata provided to E-RIHS should include an applicable licence, legal restrictions, and any additional conditions of use of copyrightable data that they are assigned to.
- Where the Creative Commons tools and licenses are not appropriate or cannot be used the metadata shall include a rights statements provided by RightsStatements.org⁹ which communicates the copyright and re-use status of digital objects.
- Metadata should be free from any restrictions and assigned a public domain waiver (for example, the CC O license).

Attribution

- E-RIHS should require Users to recognise the contributions of Data Owners, Data Providers, of E-RIHS ERIC and those of any other parties even if the relevant license or waiver does not require so.

Embargo Period

- Data Owners and Data Providers shall have the right to apply an embargo period, not exceeding 5 years. The use of such right should be exercised with diligence while minimised to the extent possible necessary, following the principle “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”.

Traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expression

- In cases of TK and TCE, where the use of the digital object is not restricted by copyright and/or related rights but where laws (in one or more jurisdictions) other than copyright impose restrictions on the use of the object, the No Copyright – Other Known Legal Restrictions Right Statement should be used.¹⁰

⁹ <https://rightsstatements.org/en/>

¹⁰ <http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/NoC-OKLR/1.0/>

Proprietary use and protection of IPR

- If certain IPR generated by Partners or by E-RIHS ERIC are capable of industrial or commercial exploitation, that Party or E-RIHS ERIC may consider how such Foreground could be exploited and how the allocation of rights among Partners should be done.
- In such cases, E-RIHS ERIC or the Partner should ensure that the IP is protected and exploited in a manner that recognises the contributions of individuals, their organisations and those of any other parties. If there is a potential for such commercial exploitation, an investigation whether there is an interest by private entities in creating marketable products should be carried out.
- Relevant considerations for protecting Foreground may include (but are not limited to):
 - Where the intellectual property has substantial potential for commercial exploitation, supported by business case analysis, for example, the creation of new services, technology transfer etc. that may justify protection of the IP or strict confidentiality obligations.
 - Where it is deemed that for cross-licensing, technology transfer or for other legitimate reasons the intellectual property should be protected.
 - In cases of particularly important inventions or creation where it is deemed that the impact and visibility in the scientific community will be maximised by such measures (i.e., patent protection).

Liability

- E-RIHS ERIC disclaims all representations and warranties of any kind related to the use of any products and/or intellectual property resulting from E-RIHS ERIC activities.

Responsibilities of Data Owners, Data Providers and Partners

When sharing data through E-RIHS ERIC, Data Owners and Data Providers shall be responsible:

- To provide such data after applying measures to restrict access to sensitive data (such as confidential data, protection of endangered species, etc.)
- To comply with legal and ethical requirements regarding the disclosure of data, such as, but not limited to, GDPR, confidentiality, national security constraints and other regulatory requirements. For this purpose Data Owners and Data Providers may use various methods, such as data generalisation, data anonymisation, or simply restricting any access to the relevant data.

- To provide the required minimum subset of metadata, including unique identifiers, along with the data provided, in both machine and human readable format in order to enable advanced research techniques.
- To assign an appropriate license in accordance with this policy in both machine and human readable format and to assign the CC 0 license (or equivalent) to the metadata.
- To liaise and collaborate with the E-RIHS ERIC data management team in order to maintain and manage the data and improve its quality.
- To ensure accuracy of the data provided.
- In case the data is provided by a third party Data Provider (who is not the Data Owner), to warrant that the data may be made available through E-RIHS ERIC and to acknowledge that E-RIHS ERIC is authorised to maintain, reproduce, distribute, and re-use the data for users.

E-RIHS Partners further agree:

- to comply with the principles set out in this Implementation strategy for IPR management.
- that they have no right to any Background IP that any other Partner brings to E-RIHS, other than as expressly set out in this Implementation strategy for IPR management and/or applicable license.
- Acknowledge that they have no right to TK and TCE that is made available to them through E-RIHS.
- Ensure that appropriate clauses, reflecting the requirements of this policy, are included in service agreements, employment contracts, sub-contractors, in-kind agreements and other relevant agreements.

7. Implementation

The following implementation measures and licenses are recommended for use by E-RIHS Partners, Data Owners and Data Providers when making their research data available through the E-RIHS ERIC on the basis of open licensing:

Research object	Recommended license	Comments
Metadata	CC 0	Or equivalent
Data	CC 0 CC-BY	Or equivalent, unless legal restrictions, legitimate reasons or other justified considerations apply.
Database	CC 0 PDDL CC-BY ODC-By	Or equivalent
Bespoke software	An Open-Source Initiative (OSI) approved license	https://opensource.org/licenses/
Proprietary data	N/A	To be assessed on a case-by-case basis.
TK and TCE	“No Copyright - Other Known Legal Restrictions” or equivalent statement of rights.	http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/NoC-OKLR/1.0/

8. Conclusions

E-RIHS ERIC is unlikely to own the heritage research objects or data but it is envisaged that E-RIHS ERIC will facilitate the sharing of the scientific benefit of its Partners' work with the user community, among others, through a system of open licensing. While doing so, E-RIHS should consider Partners' data-sovereignty as well as legitimate and regulatory concerns. As a general rule, the impact of copyrights and other forms of IPR should be minimised to the extent possible, by using appropriate open licenses, and shall not become an obstacle to the use, reuse and sharing of data by users of E-RIHS. However, in justified cases, Open Access principles should be balanced against legal restrictions and legitimate interests. Measures used to restrict access to sensitive data may include embargo periods, authorisation procedures, specific contractual arrangements and licenses other than the CC BY recommended above.

Collection, storage and curation of data should be done with accurate metadata so as to fulfil the FAIR principles. The metadata should include a statement of rights, legal restrictions, applicable licences, and any additional conditions of use of copyrightable data that they are assigned to.

In specific cases, E-RIHS should explore the possibility whether the activities it carries out under its work programmes generate IPR with a potential for commercial exploitation. Whenever certain IPR generated by a Partner or by E-RIHS ERIC is capable of industrial or commercial exploitation, that Partner, or E-RIHS ERIC, as the case may be, should examine whether it can retain the Foreground and pursue its appropriate protection (subject to the considerations mentioned above regarding protection). IPR created, obtained, or developed by Partners should be owned by those Partners.

E-RIHS Partners, Data Owner and Data Providers are expected to comply with Sections 6 and 7 of this IPR Management Strategy when making their research data available through the E-RIHS ERIC.